

Reversible Logic-Based Cryptography Design for Secure and Efficient Data Processing

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To Cite this Article

Dr. D Naga Ravikiran, SK Afrin, Y Tejaswini, S Pooja Sushmitha & V Nagireddy (2025). Reversible Logic-Based Cryptography Design for Secure and Efficient Data Processing . International Journal for Modern Trends in Science and Technology, 11(03), 244-253. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15093949>

Article Info

Received: 27 February 2025; Accepted: 21 March 2025.; Published: 26 March 2025.

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KEYWORDS

Reversible Logic,
Cryptography,
FPGA,
Data Security

ABSTRACT

Reversible logic synthesis and testing have emerged as crucial research areas due to their significance in low-power design and quantum computing. Reversible computing finds applications in various fields, including quantum computing, nanotechnology, digital signal processing, and bioinformatics. These applications require robust cryptographic mechanisms to prevent unauthorized access and ensure data confidentiality. However, conventional cryptographic algorithms often face challenges related to high area and power consumption. To address these issues, this work proposes a Reversible Logic Gates Cryptography Design (RLGCD) for secure encryption and decryption. A Linear Feedback Shift Register (LFSR) is utilized to generate cryptographic keys for both processes. Additionally, to enhance data security, watermarking is incorporated using the Least Significant Bit (LSB) method. The FPGA-based performance evaluation of the RLGCD architecture demonstrates significant improvements over conventional cryptographic approaches in terms of efficiency and security.

1. INTRODUCTION

Reversible logic has gained significant attention in recent years due to its ability to minimize power dissipation, which is a critical requirement in low-power Very Large Scale Integration (VLSI) design. It has diverse applications in low-power CMOS circuits,

optical information processing, DNA computing, quantum computation, and nanotechnology. Traditional irreversible hardware computations lead to energy dissipation due to information loss. According to Landauer's principle, the loss of each bit of information results in heat dissipation of $KT \ln(2)$ joules, where K is

the Boltzmann constant and T is the temperature in Kelvin. While this energy loss is negligible at the individual bit level, large-scale high-speed computations generate excessive heat, adversely affecting system performance and component lifespan.

Bennett demonstrated in 1973 that this energy dissipation can be mitigated if a system allows the reproduction of inputs from observed outputs, thereby making computations reversible. In reversible logic, computations can run both forward and backward, ensuring that the input states can be uniquely retrieved from the output states. This one-to-one correspondence between inputs and outputs prevents information loss, thereby reducing energy dissipation. Although perfect physical reversibility is theoretically unattainable, reversible circuits significantly minimize heat dissipation by gradually shifting charge between circuit nodes rather than changing voltage levels abruptly. As a result, reversible computing plays a crucial role in optimizing digital logic designs and is expected to impact instruction sets, high-level programming languages, and future computing architectures.

Reversible Logic in Cryptography

Cryptography, the practice of securing information by converting it into an unreadable format, is essential for maintaining data confidentiality. It involves transforming plaintext into ciphertext through encryption and restoring the original plaintext via decryption. In modern VLSI design, a major challenge is heat dissipation, especially as transistor densities continue to increase following Moore's Law. The growing demand for secure communication systems further emphasizes the need for cryptographic techniques that not only provide strong security but also operate efficiently in terms of power and area.

Conventional cryptographic algorithms, while highly secure, often consume significant power due to complex computations. Reversible logic presents an effective solution by enabling cryptographic operations with minimal energy loss. The **Reversible Logic Gate Cryptography Design (RLGCD)** proposed in this paper leverages reversible logic for both encryption and decryption processes. This approach enhances energy efficiency compared to conventional cryptographic methods, making it suitable for applications in fields such as medical data security, banking, and government communications. The cryptographic key is generated

using a Linear Feedback Shift Register (LFSR), ensuring robust security.

Data Security and Multi-Level Encryption

With the increasing volume of data transmitted over networks, ensuring security has become paramount. Various cryptographic techniques, including encryption and digital certificates, are employed to safeguard sensitive information. Multi-level encryption, an advanced cryptographic approach, enhances security by encrypting data multiple times using the same or different keys and algorithms. This method strengthens protection against cyber threats by making decryption more complex for unauthorized users.

Cryptographic systems are categorized into **symmetric** and **asymmetric** key algorithms. **Symmetric-key algorithms**, also known as private-key algorithms, require the sender and receiver to share the same key for both encryption and decryption. While these methods are highly efficient, they lack authentication mechanisms. In contrast, **asymmetric-key algorithms**, or public-key cryptographic techniques, use separate keys for encryption and decryption, enhancing security but demanding greater computational resources. Examples include RSA, Rabin, and ElGamal encryption.

This paper explores the implementation of **multi-level encryption using reversible logic** to achieve enhanced security while maintaining computational efficiency. By integrating reversible logic with cryptographic techniques, the proposed system provides improved security, energy efficiency, and optimized FPGA performance compared to conventional cryptographic architectures.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Architecture Design and VLSI Hardware Implementation of Image Encryption/Decryption System Using Re-configurable 2-D Von Neumann Cellular Automata

Authors:Rong-Jian Chen, Yi-TE Lai, Jui-Lin Lai

This study presents the first architecture design and VLSI hardware implementation of an image encryption/decryption system using re-configurable two-dimensional (2-D) von Neumann cellular automata (CA). The encryption method is based on pixel value substitution through progressive CA transformation. A **16 × 16 re-configurable 2-D von Neumann CA** is employed to generate high-quality random sequences,

functioning as a key stream. This structure allows for flexible configurations, generating a **single 256-cell CA**, four **8 × 8 CA sets**, or sixteen **4 × 4 CA sets**. Simulations were conducted using **CADENCE tools**, and circuit synthesis was performed using **SYNOPTIS tools** with a **TSMC 0.18μm cell library**. The resulting implementation achieved a **total area of 15.6816 mm²**, a **maximum operating frequency of 100 MHz**, and **27.74 mW total dynamic power**, demonstrating its suitability for VLSI-based cryptographic applications.

A Nonlinear Equation-Based Cryptosystem for Image Encryption and Decryption

Authors:RithmiMitter, M. SrideviSathyaPriya

This paper introduces a novel image encryption and decryption technique that integrates **chaotic maps** with a **nonlinear BB (Brahmagupta-Bhaskara) equation** to enhance security. While chaotic map-based encryption methods have been widely explored, they often suffer from vulnerabilities, making them susceptible to attacks. The proposed method leverages the **BB equation** to introduce nonlinear dependency, thereby strengthening the encryption process. A VLSI architecture for this cryptographic approach was designed and implemented using **Xilinx ISE software**, enabling efficient hardware realization for secure image processing applications.

VLSI Realization of a Secure Cryptosystem for Image Encryption and Decryption

Authors: K. DurghaRao, Ch. Gangadhar

This work extends previous research on chaotic map-based encryption methods by incorporating the **BB equation** to overcome security challenges. The paper proposes new encryption and decryption algorithms that improve cryptographic security by integrating chaos theory with mathematical equations. The algorithms are demonstrated through examples, and their **VLSI architectures** are designed and implemented using **Xilinx ISE software** for hardware deployment. Furthermore, the **hardware complexity** of the proposed approach is analyzed and compared with existing cryptographic models, highlighting its efficiency in secure image encryption.

Implementation of Encryption and Decryption Algorithms for Security of Mobile Devices

Authors: B.V. Varun, Abhishek M.V., AkshayChanabasappaGangadhar

With the advancement of **mobile communication** and **VLSI technology**, the demand for secure data processing

on smart devices has increased. This study focuses on implementing encryption and decryption algorithms to enhance data security in mobile environments. Given that sensitive information is often stored on mobile devices or cloud platforms, robust encryption techniques are essential to prevent unauthorized access. The paper discusses various **symmetric and asymmetric cryptographic methods**, considering their impact on processing delay and computational complexity. The proposed algorithm offers improved security with reduced processing time, achieving a **10% enhancement in contact encryption** and a **15% improvement in image encryption** compared to conventional methods. Experimental results confirm its effectiveness across multiple platforms, making it a viable solution for mobile security applications.

3.PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

Reversible Logic Gates (RLGs):

RLGs are the circuits that having equal number of inputs and outputs with a unique one to one mapping relationship. Thus it is possible to recover the input pattern from the output pattern, so that there is no information loss during computation. For example, let 110 is the pattern which is given as input to RLG. Then after completing the logic operation it produce 001 as output. If we apply this 001 as input and obtained 110 as output then it depicts the occurrence of a reversible operation. while using traditional combinational logic circuits, for every bit of data that is lost during operation there will be an equivalent heat energy dissipation. The reason behind this is according to the second law of thermodynamics there is no way to reproduce the information once lost. So when the computation is performed in a reversible manner then it is possible to achieve a logical zero power dissipation. i.e., there is no decrease in the entropy of the system. Constraints for designing RLGs include

- RLGs do not allow fanout.
- Quantum cost should be minimum as possible.
- Optimize the design to make garbage outputs minimum.

A reversible logic circuits should have least gate level. The original motivation was that reversible gates dissipate less heat (or, in principle, no heat). In a normal gate, input states are lost, since less information is present in the output than was present at the input. This loss of information loses energy to the surrounding area as heat, because of thermodynamic entropy. Another way to understand this is that charges on a circuit are grounded and thus flow away, taking a small quantity of

energy with them when they change state. A reversible gate only moves the states around, and since no information is lost, energy is conserved.

Universality and Toffoli gate

Any reversible gate must have the same number of input and output bits, by the pigeonhole principle. For one input bit, there are two possible reversible gates. One of them is NOT. The other is the identity gate which maps its input to the output unchanged. For two input bits, the only non-trivial gate is the controlled NOT gate which XORs the first bit to the second bit and leaves the first bit unchanged.

Truth table	Permutation matrix form										
<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>INPUT</th> <th>OUTPUT</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr><td>0</td><td>0</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>1</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>0</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>1</td></tr> </tbody> </table>	INPUT	OUTPUT	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$
INPUT	OUTPUT										
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0	1										
1	0										
1	1										

Unfortunately, there are reversible functions that cannot be computed using just those gates. In other words, the set consisting of NOT and XOR gates is not universal. If we want to compute an arbitrary function using reversible gates, we need another gate. One possibility is the Toffoli gate, proposed in 1980 by Toffoli. This gate has 3-bit inputs and outputs. If the first two bits are set, it flips the third bit. The following is a table of the input and output bits:

Truth table	Permutation matrix form										
<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>INPUT</th> <th>OUTPUT</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr><td>0</td><td>0</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>1</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>0</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>1</td></tr> </tbody> </table>	INPUT	OUTPUT	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$
INPUT	OUTPUT										
0	0										
0	1										
1	0										
1	1										

It can be also described as mapping bits a, b and c to a, b and c XOR (a AND b).

The Toffoli gate is universal; this means that for any Boolean function $f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m)$, there is a circuit consisting of Toffoli gates which takes x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m and some extra bits set to 0 or 1 and outputs $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m, f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m)$, and some extra bits (called garbage). Essentially, this means that one can use Toffoli gates to build systems that will perform any desired Boolean function computation in a reversible manner.

Fredkin gate

Figure 1: Circuit representation of Fredkin gate

The Fredkin gate (also CSWAP gate) is a computational circuit suitable for reversible computing, invented by Ed Fredkin. It is universal, which means that any logical or arithmetic operation can be constructed entirely of Fredkin gates. The Fredkin gate is the three-bit gate that swaps the last two bits if the first bit is 1.

The basic Fredkin gate is a controlled swap gate that maps three inputs (C, I₁, I₂) onto three outputs (C, O₁, O₂). The C input is mapped directly to the C output. If C = 0, no swap is performed; I₁ maps to O₁, and I₂ maps to O₂. Otherwise, the two outputs are swapped so that I₁ maps to O₂, and I₂ maps to O₁. It is easy to see that this circuit is reversible, i.e., "undoes itself" when run backwards. A generalized n×n Fredkin gate passes its first n-2 inputs unchanged to the corresponding outputs, and swaps its last two outputs if and only if the first n-2 inputs are all 1. The Fredkin gate is the reversible three-bit gate that swaps the last two bits if the first bit is 1.

Truth table	Matrix form																																																								
<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>INPUT</th> <th>OUTPUT</th> </tr> <tr> <th>C</th> <th>I₁</th> <th>I₂</th> <th>C</th> <th>O₁</th> <th>O₂</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr><td>0</td><td>0</td><td>0</td><td>0</td><td>0</td><td>0</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>0</td><td>1</td><td>0</td><td>0</td><td>1</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>1</td><td>0</td><td>0</td><td>1</td><td>0</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>1</td><td>1</td><td>0</td><td>1</td><td>1</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>0</td><td>0</td><td>1</td><td>0</td><td>0</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>0</td><td>1</td><td>1</td><td>0</td><td>1</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>1</td><td>0</td><td>1</td><td>0</td><td>1</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>1</td><td>1</td><td>1</td><td>1</td><td>1</td></tr> </tbody> </table>	INPUT	OUTPUT	C	I ₁	I ₂	C	O ₁	O ₂	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$
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It has the useful property that the numbers of 0s and 1s are conserved throughout, which in the billiard ball model means the same number of balls are output as input. This corresponds nicely to the conservation of mass in physics, and helps to show that the model is not wasteful.

Logic function with XOR and AND gates

$O_1 = I_1 \text{ XOR } S$
 $O_2 = I_2 \text{ XOR } S$
 with $S = (I_1 \text{ XOR } I_2) \text{ AND } C$

It can also be implemented by the following logic:

$$O_1 = (\text{NOT } C \text{ AND } I_1) \text{ OR } (C \text{ AND } I_2) = CI_1 + CI_2$$

$$O_2 = (C \text{ AND } I_1) \text{ OR } (\text{NOT } C \text{ AND } I_2) = CI_1 + CI_2$$

$$C_{out} = C_{in}$$

Feynman gate

Feynman gate is a 2*2 one through reversible gate as shown in figure 1. The input vector is I(A, B) and the output vector is O(P, Q). The outputs are defined by $P=A$, $Q=A \oplus B$. Quantum cost of a Feynman gate is 1. Feynman Gate (FG) can be used as a copying gate. Since a fan out is not allowed in reversible logic, this gate is useful for duplication of the required outputs.

Figure 2: Feynman Gate

Table 1: Truth table of Feynman gates

A	B	P	Q
0	0	0	0
0	1	0	1
1	0	1	1
1	1	1	0

Double Feynman Gate (F2G)

Figure 3 shows a 3*3 Double Feynman gate. The input vector is I(A, B, C) and the output vector is O(P, Q, R). The outputs are defined by $P = A$, $Q = A \oplus B$, $R = A \oplus C$. Quantum cost of double Feynman gate is 2.

Figure 3: Double Feynman gate

Table 2: Truth table of double Feynman gates

A	B	C	P	Q	R
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	1	0	0	1
0	1	0	0	1	0
0	1	1	0	1	1
1	0	0	1	1	1
1	0	1	1	1	0
1	1	0	1	0	1
1	1	1	1	0	0

Peres Gate

Figure 4 a 3*3 Peres gate. The input vector is I(A, B, C) and the output vector is O(P, Q, R). The output is defined by $P = A$, $Q = A \oplus B$ and $R = AB \oplus C$. Quantum cost of a Peres gate is 4. In the proposed design Peres gate is used because of its lowest quantum cost.

Figure 4: Peres gate

Table 3: Truth table of peres gate

A	B	C	P	Q	R
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	1	0	0	1
0	1	0	0	1	0
0	1	1	0	1	1
1	0	0	1	1	0
1	0	1	1	1	1
1	1	0	1	0	1
1	1	1	1	0	0

A full-adder using two Peres gates is as shown in figure 5. The quantum realization of this shows that its quantum cost is 8 two Peres gates are used.

Figure 5: Full adder using two Peres gates

A single 4*4 reversible gate called PFAG gate with quantum cost of 8 is used to realize the multiplier.

TSG Gate

Figure 6 shows a 4*4 TSG gate. The input vector is I(A, B, C, D) and the output vector is O(P, Q, R, S). The output is defined by $P = A$, $Q = A'C' \odot B'$, $R = (A'C' \odot B') \odot D$ and $S = (A'C' \odot B') \cdot D \odot (AB \odot C)$ Quantum cost of a Peres

gate is 4. In the proposed design Peres gate is used because of its lowest quantum cost. It can be verified that the input pattern corresponding to a particular output pattern can be uniquely determined. The proposed TSG gate is capable of implementing all Boolean functions and can also work singly as a reversible Full adder

Figure 6: TSG gate

Figure 7: TSG Gate Working As Reversible Full Adder

The RLG that are used to design this new cryptography system includes Feynman gate, Fredkin gate, Toffoli's gate and SCL gates and are shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Block diagram of RLGs

Encryption process:

The encryption process is shown in Figure 9. The pixel values are thus 8 bit binary word: $i[0], i[1], i[2], i[3], i[4], i[5], i[6], i[7]$. The first four LSB input bits is applied to the below SCL gate and the above SCL gate is fed by the first four MSB.

Figure 9: Encryption block

Four of these inputs complete the SCL gate operation and thus produce four result bits. The first three LSB outputs from the below SCL gate perform Toffoli gate operation and provides three different output bits. Similarly the first three MSB value outputs of SCL gate feed Toffoli gate and provides three output bits. One of the output bits from the above and below SCL gates perform Feynman gate operation. Both Toffoli gates are followed by Fredkin gate and thus its outputs perform Fredkin gate. The Fredkin gate outputs and the Feynman gate outputs are connected to the XOR gates and thus perform XOR operation with LFSR key. Then, the XOR gate output provides the encrypted binary image pixel value $e[0], e[1], e[2], e[3], e[4], e[5], e[6], e[7]$.

Decryption process:

The process of decryption is shown in Figure 10. The decryption process is just the reverse operation of the encryption. Thus, encryption process output is fed as input to decryption process block. First, the encrypted pixel bits perform XOR operation with the key generated by the LFSR. After performing the four reversible gate operation one followed by the next the decrypted outputs are obtained at the SCL gate output. The decrypted output eight bit pixel values are $d[0], d[1], d[2], d[3], d[4], d[5], d[6], d[7]$. The encrypted as well as the decrypted binary output values are written into a text file. In MATLAB encrypted image and decrypted image are generated from the output text file.

Figure 10: Decryption block

ADVANTAGES:

Low power consumption: Reversible logic gates consume less power than conventional logic gates because they do not lose information during computation. This is because reversible logic gates use feedback to generate their outputs, which allows them to reuse the same inputs multiple times.

Reduced heat dissipation: Reversible logic gates dissipate less heat than conventional logic gates because they do not generate garbage outputs. Garbage outputs are outputs that are not needed for the computation, but

are generated anyway. Conventional logic gates can generate garbage outputs, which can lead to increased heat dissipation.

Improved security: Reversible logic gates can be used to implement more secure encryption and decryption algorithms than conventional logic gates. This is because reversible logic gates are more resistant to power analysis attacks. Power analysis attacks are a type of attack that can be used to extract secret information from a system by analyzing its power consumption. Reversible logic gates are more resistant to power analysis attacks because they do not generate garbage outputs, which can be used by attackers to extract secret information.

Suitability for quantum computing: Reversible logic gates are well-suited for implementation in quantum computers. This is because reversible logic gates are unitary operations, which are the building blocks of quantum computation. Unitary operations are operations that preserve the information content of a quantum state. Reversible logic gates are unitary operations, which mean that they can be used to implement quantum encryption and decryption algorithms.

4. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Simulation Result:

Figure 11: The simulation result of Encryption, in this we applied input plane test, clock and reset based on that encrypted output is generated.

Figure 12: The simulation result of Decryption, in this we applied encrypted input, clock and reset based on that decrypted output is generated.

BLOCK DIAGRAM

Figure 13: The block diagram of encryption in this we applied input data (a(7:0), clk, rst), we generated output data (encrypted e(7:0)).

Figure 14: The block diagram of Decryption in this we applied input data (e(7:0), clk, rst), we generated output data (decrypted d(7:0)).

RTL SCHEMATIC

Figure 15: The RTL schematic of encryption process in this .we have different types of gates (SCL,TOOFOL,FRADKEN,FEYMAN & XOR) to get output.

Figure 16: The RTL schematic of decryption process in this .we have different types of gates (SCL,TOOFOL,FRADKEN,FEYMAN & XOR) to get output.

Device utilization summary:

Figure 17: Area Report of encryption operation in this we required 12 lookup tables to perform this operation.

Figure 18: Area Report of decryption operation in this we required 14 lookup tables to perform this operation.

Timing Summary:

Figure 19: Delay Report shows the encryption in this we get delay value of circuit is 6.954ns.

Figure 20: Delay Report of the decryption

5.CONCLUSIONS

This study introduces a Reversible Logic Gate Cryptography Design (RLGCD) utilizing an LFSR key and watermarking for enhanced security. The

cryptographic system is designed using Feynman, Fredkin, Toffoli, and SCL gates, ensuring both high security and low power consumption, making it superior to conventional approaches.

The encryption and decryption processes are implemented in Xilinx ISE, where input pixel values are processed from a text file. The proposed RLGCD architecture, comprising an LFSR, encryption block, and decryption block, supports both grayscale and color images. Additionally, watermarking using the Least Significant Bit (LSB) technique is incorporated to further strengthen data security. Performance evaluation on the Spartan-3E XC3S500E FPGA device demonstrates significant improvements over existing cryptographic systems.

As reversible logic gates play a crucial role in quantum computing, advancements in cryptographic designs based on these gates contribute to the progress of quantum logic circuits. Since RLGCD is successfully implemented using Verilog, it holds strong potential for future deployment on ASIC platforms, paving the way for more efficient and secure cryptographic solutions.

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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